

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.21204939

SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS: A CASE STUDY OF CURITÍ, COLOMBIA

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Received: 12/04/2026

Accepted: 26/05/2026

ABSTRACT

The aim of the research was to assess the changes generated in the studied resort, in order to propose actions that contribute to the minimization and prevention of environmental impacts generated in the municipality of Curití, promoting sustainable tourism in the region. The methodology focused on a mixed research model aimed at gathering, identifying and addressing various aspects of the study, integrating quantitative and qualitative information. The results obtained from the analysis of the information showed that the municipality of Curití, which belongs to the province of Guantá in the department of Santander, is known for its natural wealth and its proximity to important tourist destinations such as San Gil and the Chicamocha National Park in the Eastern Andes of Colombia. During the characterization of the Curití Gorge, high levels of turbidity and the presence of coliforms were detected, in addition, the local community expressed a growing concern about the environmental deterioration of the area, highlighting that the growth of tourism has generated negative impacts on natural resources. In accordance with the environmental impact assessment, water was found to be the most affected environmental factor. It was concluded that the local population showed a significant willingness towards environmental education, perceiving it as a key tool for improving the quality of the environment. In this regard, actions aimed at sustainable tourism and training on environmental issues were identified and promoted.

KEYWORDS: Water Quality, Sustainable Development, Ecotourism, Environmental Education, Environmental Impact.

1. INTRODUCTION

The municipality of Curití is known for its scenic beauty and its richness in terms of biodiversity, which is why tourism demand and development has been increasing, according to what is proposed in the tourism strategy for Colombia (Ministry of Commerce, Industry and Tourism, 2023). This economic line is characterized by being an important source of income for the community of the municipality of Curití, generating employment opportunities in the region. However, it also represents negative consequences on the environment and the coexistence of people (Montañez and Corzo, 2022).

Consequently, sustainable tourism has emerged as a competitiveness strategy in the economic initiatives of the population, becoming a very relevant alternative, especially in areas with high ecological and cultural value such as the spa and its surrounding area (Navas and Téllez, 2023). In fact, in the sustainable development goals proposed at the global level, goal number eight mentions and ratifies decent work and economic development through the promotion of sustainable tourism for job creation and the promotion of local culture (United Nations, 2015).

This research has the objective of establishing sustainable tourism strategies, proposing actions that contribute to the minimization and prevention of environmental impacts generated in a spa in the municipality of Colombia, promoting sustainable tourism in the region. The above, through a descriptive methodology of primary and secondary information that included processes such as the monitoring of the Curití stream, the analysis of the community's perception regarding the problem of unsustainable tourism and the evaluation of environmental impacts for the ratification of the importance of environmental education and the promotion of ecotourism (Cuz, 2021).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Camila Álvarez Muñoz and Cristian Mantilla Valbuena, evaluated environmental strategies in the tourism sector of several municipalities in the upper and middle basin of the Fonce River, with the use of water governance elements, using surveys directed at tourist operators, the criteria of governance of international organizations and the National Policy for the Comprehensive Management of Water Resources. The results showed a low level of water governance, highlighting the need to improve effectiveness, efficiency, communication and culture. It was suggested to increase economic resources and strengthen technical support from local authorities

and organizations to develop strategies that positively impact water governance in the region (Álvarez and Mantilla, 2019).

Mercedes Chino Escalante investigated the environmental impacts of the tourist influx on Los Palos beach, in Tacna, using the Rapid Environmental Impact Assessment (RIAM) methodology. Field visits were carried out to collect information on tourist activities and the RIAM matrix was applied, identifying 11 environmental impacts, of which 7 were negative and 4 positives. The positive impacts, associated with the socioeconomic and cultural component, included slight benefits. In contrast, the negative impacts included 6 slight impacts and 1 significant, the latter being related to the poor disposal of solid waste. Chino concluded that these negative impacts could be mitigated through the implementation of environmental improvement proposals by local authorities (Chino, 2019).

Lesly Bricet Chávez Sandoval and Valeria Meléndez Rospigliosi analyzed the economic, environmental and sociocultural impacts of tourism in the Huacachina resort. Using a qualitative - phenomenological approach, they interviewed 12 residents to obtain their perceptions about tourism. Socioeconomically, tourism generated income for some residents, mainly business owners, although investment in new tourism businesses is complicated due to saturation of space. Environmentally, the Huacachina lagoon suffered from contamination by food waste and plastics, affecting both residents and local fauna. The construction of new establishments and the activity of the tubulars also negatively impacted the dunes. Socioculturally, no significant impact on the identity of the residents was observed, although the arrival of Venezuelan migrants generated labor tensions (Chávez and Meléndez, 2019).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. *Environmental Baseline*

The environmental baseline was made up of qualitative data on relevant aspects of the municipality and the media that are part of the surrounding environment of the municipality and the spa (Bagur, 2021). The main tool for obtaining information was the bibliographic review of documents, magazines, geographic viewers and websites such as that of the Municipal Mayor's Office, the Government of Santander, the IDEAM, among others. The location of the municipality is reflected in Fig 1.

Fig.1: Location Of the Municipality of Curití.

B. Characterization of the Curití Stream

Using the Google Earth tool, the delimitation of the area to be monitored was carried out to obtain

relevant information for the visits such as roads, water sources, urban area, homes, etc. And the body of water to monitor (see Fig. 2)

Fig. 2: Monitoring Point in Quebrada Curití.

To measure the flow, a system of stakes and ropes was used to define the area where the flow measurement would be carried out. To calculate the flow, the float method was used (Chamorro, 2011). The sampling was carried out consecutively for 12

hours and the day concluded at 6 p.m., with the preparation of the composite sample.

The implemented parameters and methods are shown in Table 1.):

Table 1: Parameters And Detection Methods.

Parameter	Method	Units
Temperature	SM 2550 B	°C
pH	SM 4500 H+ B	pH units
Dissolved Oxygen	ASTM D888-18, Método C	mg O ₂ /L
DBO ₅	SM 5210 B, SM 4500 O G	mg O ₂ /L
DQO	SM 5220 C	mg O ₂ /L
SDT	SM 2540 C	mg/l
Turbidity	SM 2130 B	NTU
Phosphorus	SM 4500 P E	mg P - PO ₄ /L

Nitrates	J. Roeder Adsorption Spectrometry Method, 9a Ed,2009	mg NO ₃ - -N/L
Coliforms	SM 9221 E, SM 9221 B	NMP / 100 mL

Subsequently, a survey was carried out aimed at residents, tourists and merchants in the study area; which was validated respectively by expert judgment and analyzed based on statistical variables such as the standard deviation in the SPSS Statistics software (Burgos et al., 2022).

A. Environmental Assessment

For the evaluation of environmental impacts, the Simplified Conesa methodology was taken into account, proposed in the Manual for Environmental Evaluation by Jorge Arboleda, based on the identification of the impact-generating activities and the relationship of these with the environment to the generation of impacts (Conesa, 2011).

Table 2: Levels Of Importance of Impacts.

Importance	Qualification Range
LOW	< 25
MODERATE	25 ≥ < 50
SEVERE	50 ≥
CRITICAL	≥ 75
NULL	+

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Environmental Baseline

The municipality of Colombia recorded an average annual precipitation of 1,825 millimeters for the high area and 1,115 millimeters for the low area, with a temperature that ranges between 4.6 to 30 °C, depending on the height of the terrain (Ramírez, 2021).

The hydrological network of the municipality stands out mainly for the presence of the Curití micro-basin and part of the Cuchicute stream; Spatially at the national level, it is located within the hydrographic network of the Fonce, Suárez, Sogamoso river basins and the great Magdalena basin (Ramírez, 2021).

Regarding geology, the Girón formation, Tambor formation, Rosa Blanca formation, Paja formation, Tablazo formation and the Simití formation were found. This area is characterized by being influenced by the action of the Aratocha-Los Santos fault towards

the east of the municipality and by the Riachuelo-Curití fault system, since these faults are oriented in a NW-SE direction (Unión Temporal Curití, 2023).

The use of land in the municipality is mainly intended for agriculture, in the rural area such activities are concentrated, such as: planting crops, livestock, poultry and fish farming. On the other hand, the construction of tertiary roads and homes, and some properties for tourist activities due to the ecosystems present in the area (IGAC, 2017).

The urban and rural area of the municipality is generally made up of 10 neighborhoods and 39 villages defined at the cadastral level; with a total of 12,717 inhabitants (DANE, 2019).

A. Characterization of the Curití Ravine

The parameters evaluated in the laboratory considered for the calculation of the IRCA defined as the Risk Index of the Quality of Water for Human Consumption were defined as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Analyzed Parameters and IRCA Calculation.

EVALUATED PARAMETER	VALUE	UNITS	RESOLUTION 2115 DE 2007	SCORE IRCA	fulfillment
Turbidity	4,2	NTU	2	15	NO
pH	6,99	Unidades de pH	6,5 - 9,0	1,5	SI
Phosphates	< 0,03	Mg P - PO ₄ ³⁻ / L	0,5	1	SI
Nitrates	< 0,10	Mg NO ₃ ⁻ - N/L	10	1	SI
Total coliforms	170	NMP / 100 mL	0	15	NO
Total			33,5		
IRCA			89,55		

The value obtained for turbidity was shown to exceed the maximum values given by Resolution 2115 of 2007. This non-compliance is due to the presence of many solids in the water that affected

other parameters such as color, flavor and even the incidence of turbidity. sunlight and oxygen that sustain aquatic life. Resolution 2115 of 2007 establishes that there must be a total absence of

coliforms in water intended for human consumption, since their presence represents a health risk. In this case, a value of 180 was obtained, which indicates a significant non-compliance with the permitted limits, becoming a determining factor in the IRCA evaluation. As shown in the formula.

Formula 1.

$$IRCA(\%) = \frac{\sum \text{risk scores assigned to unacceptable characteristics}}{\sum \text{risk scores assigned to all characteristics analyzed}} \times 100$$

$$IRCA(\%) = \frac{30}{33,5} \times 100$$

IRCA(%) = 89,5522%

The result of the IRCA outlined a water considered unviable sanitarly, mainly due to the presence of a high level of turbidity and the existence of coliforms, a state in relation to the possible presence of fecal matter and wastewater discharge.

A. Environmental Assessment

The Impact Generating Activities (ASPI), identified for the spa under study and their relationship with environmental factors are described in Table 3.

Table 3: Impact Receiving Factors Vs ASPI.

Component	abiotic environment					biotic environment		Socioeconomic		
	water	Air	Soil	Landscape	Climate	Flora	Fauna	Economic	Demographic	Cultural
FARI										
ASPI										
Hiking	a		b			c	d		e	f
Infrastructure construction	a		b	c		d	e	f	gg	
Use of recreational facilities	a			b			c	d	e	
Use of wood stoves for recreational activities	a	b	c		d	e	f		g	
outdoor camp	a		b	c		d	e	f		
Immersion in water	a			b			c	d	e	
Restaurant operation	a	b	c	d	e			f	g	
Track maintenance	a	b	c					d	e	
Tourist traffic and transportation	a	b	c					d	e	f
Commercial activities	a		b	c		d	e	f	g	

Activities linked to tourism in the study area turned out to be those that generated the greatest number of damages and were directly related to environmental impacts. Among these activities, hiking, the use of wood stoves for recreation and outdoor camping stand out.

The environmental factors with a high interaction

index were water and soil, the demographic and economic part followed, respectively, other factors such as fauna, landscape, flora and air were found with lower interactions. Finally, two factors were found with a minimum number of interactions, climate and cultural aspects. This relationship is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Interaction Of Environmental Factors With ASPI.

The quantification of the identified impacts is broken down in Table 4.

Table 4: Quantification of the Magnitude of Environmental Impacts.

C	Impacts	IN	EX	MO	PE	RV	SI	AC	EF	PR	RC	CA	Importance
-	Alteration in the visual perception of the landscape	2	2	8	4	2	2	4	4	2	4	40	Moderate
-	Alteration in the characteristics of the soil	4	4	8	4	2	4	4	4	4	4	54	Severe
-	Alteration in the physicochemical properties of water	8	8	4	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	68	Severe
-	Alteration of behavioral patterns of fauna	2	2	2	4	4	2	1	1	1	4	29	Moderate
-	Artification of the environment	4	4	2	2	1	1	1	4	2	4	37	Moderate
-	Increase in the concentration of greenhouse gases	4	2	2	2	2	2	4	4	4	4	40	Moderate
-	Change in microclimate	1	1	1	4	2	2	1	1	2	4	22	Low
-	Change in land use	2	4	4	2	2	4	4	4	4	2	40	Moderate
-	Change in soil compaction	2	4	4	2	2	4	4	4	4	2	40	Moderate
-	Change in the composition of fauna species	2	2	1	4	2	2	4	1	2	4	30	Moderate
-	Change in the composition of flora species	2	1	2	2	2	1	4	4	2	4	29	Moderate
-	Change in ecosystem connectivity	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	4	23	Low
-	Change in soil structural stability	8	2	4	4	2	2	4	4	4	4	56	Severe
-	Change in architectural aesthetics	1	2	2	4	2	1	1	1	2	4	24	Low
-	Change in landscape structure	2	4	2	4	2	2	4	1	2	4	35	Moderate
-	Change in road safety	1	1	8	1	4	1	1	4	1	4	29	Moderate
-	Change in local temperature	1	1	1	4	2	2	1	1	2	4	22	Low
-	Change in population dynamics	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	4	23	Low
-	Change in physical characteristics of the soil	4	2	8	4	2	4	4	4	4	4	50	Severe
-	Change in the flow of a body of water	4	2	8	4	2	2	4	4	4	4	48	Moderate
-	Water pollution	12	8	2	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	78	Critical
-	air pollution	4	4	4	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	48	Moderate
-	Soil pollution	2	4	4	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	42	Moderate
-	Displacement of native species	2	4	4	4	2	2	4	4	2	4	40	Moderate
-	Displacement or scaring away of fauna	2	2	2	4	4	2	1	1	1	4	29	Moderate
-	Decrease in the abundance of flora species	1	2	2	4	4	2	1	1	2	4	27	Moderate
-	Decrease in the assimilation and dilution capacity of polluting substances	8	4	8	2	2	4	4	4	2	4	62	Severe
-	Decrease in water supply for human consumption	8	12	8	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	80	Critical
-	Decreased visibility	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	4	23	Low
-	Decrease in the habitat of aquatic species	4	2	4	2	2	4	4	4	2	4	42	Moderate

-	Habitat fragmentation of aquatic species	4	2	4	2	2	4	4	4	2	4	42	Moderate
-	Generation of particulate matter	4	4	8	2	4	2	4	2	4	4	50	Severe
-	Increase in the occurrence of droughts	8	4	2	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	58	Severe
-	Increase in turbidity	2	4	8	2	2	2	4	4	4	2	42	Moderate
-	Increase in solid waste in water	4	8	8	4	2	2	4	4	2	4	58	Severe
-	Increase of solids in water	2	4	8	2	2	2	4	4	4	2	42	Moderate
-	Increase in vehicular traffic	1	1	8	1	4	1	1	4	1	4	29	Moderate
-	Loss of water quality	8	12	8	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	80	Critical
-	Loss of soil quality	4	2	4	4	4	2	4	4	4	4	46	Moderate
-	Loss of the natural vocation of the resource	4	4	4	4	4	2	4	4	4	4	50	Severe
-	Risk of drowning	2	2	1	4	2	2	4	1	2	4	30	Moderate
-	Accident risk	2	2	1	4	2	2	4	1	2	4	30	Moderate
-	Vulnerability	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	19	Low
+	Increased local economic stimulus											0	Null
+	Increased local cultural pride											0	Null
+	Change in employment dynamics											0	Null
+	Change in perception of nature											0	Null
+	Change in working conditions											0	Null
+	Change in recreation activities											0	Null
+	Increase in tourist activity											0	Null
+	Increase in family income											0	Null
+	Increase in local tourism											0	Null
+	Revaluation of natural appreciation											0	Null

In the end, 53 were obtained and they were grouped as follows, 3 in critical condition, 9 in severe, 24 in moderate, 7 in low and 10 in null category, these

in null categorization are all those impacts that contribute or improve the conditions of the spa area (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: Category Of Impacts.

The natural resources that were most affected by tourist activity were water, soil and air; highlighting this first resource as it receives all the critical impacts related to water pollution, decreased water supply for human consumption and loss of water quality.

The severe impacts were focused on the soil and air resources due to the use of combustion vehicles either for transportation from the urban area to the resort or for the construction of roads and urbanization in the area of direct influence. The

movement of fauna and flora was directly related to bathing activities and adaptation of trails, camping areas and cutting trees or bushes for campfires.

The greatest number of environmental impacts were found in the moderate category, reflecting that, although there is considerable environmental impact, this can be counteracted by the application of environmental management measures (Conesa, 2011).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The municipality of Colombia stands out for its great cultural wealth and its abundance of ecosystem services, which respond effectively to tourist demands throughout the year. Its biological diversity and attractive landscapes make it a destination of high ecological and recreational value, consolidating its position as a site of interest at both a regional and national level.

The local community has demonstrated awareness of the growing need to improve the environmental quality of the ecosystem, recognizing the negative effects that tourism and other human activities have had on natural resources. In this sense, environmental education was perceived as a key tool to raise awareness among the population, and as a means to train them in the adoption of sustainable

practices in line with what was mentioned by Barrero (2020).

The finding of high levels of turbidity and the presence of coliforms in the water source studied with respect to Resolution 2115 of 2007, added to the results of the Water Quality Risk Index (IRCA) that classified it as unviable for health reasons, indicated some levels of significant contamination of water resources.

The research revealed that the increase in conventional tourism has generated an increase in environmental impacts, particularly in water quality. Although this phenomenon was linked to an important source of income for the community, it has also contributed to the degradation of the spa's natural resources.

The implementation of sustainable tourism and the development of environmental education strategies were identified as crucial and vitally important solutions to address the problem in question. The proper management of water resources, the demand, use and sustainable exploitation of ecosystems, together with the integration of sustainable environmental policies in the tourism sector, can contribute to improving the anthropic relationship with the environment and promote the sustainable development of the spa and municipality.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions: Each of the authors contributed to each of the stages of the research.

Acknowledgements: The authors especially thank the Technological Units of Santander, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering

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